

FABRICATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF 3D JUTE FABRICS REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Manufacturing and mechanical properties of three-dimensional (3D) jute fabrics composites were investigated in current research. Jute fiber yarns were used to weave orthogonal 3D preforms by a modified Dobby loom. The fiber yarns were treated with sizing agent to improve strength, so that, the yarn can be used to weave as a 3D orthogonal fabrics by the loom. The 3D fabrics after woven have been treated with an alkaline solution to remove oil and wax which inhibited by the fibers. After alkaline solution treatment, the fabrics were impregnated with epoxy and polylactic acid (PLA) resin to form 3D orthogonal jute fabric composites. The 3D jute fabric composites were tested by tension, compression, and three-point bending force on a material test system (MTS 810). The strengths, modulus and failure modes of the composites after testing were discussed in the study. Also, an Izod machine was used to estimate the impact energy of the 2D and 3D jute composites.

The 3D orthogonal jute fabric composites have better flexure strength than the 2D plain jute fabric composites. Furthermore, the 3D orthogonal jute composites have good energy absorption during bending and impacting.

Introduction

Natural fiber composites are emerging as realistic alternatives to glass reinforced composites in many applications since the 1990s. Many natural

fiber composites, which consist of natural fibers as reinforcements and a polymer-based resin as a matrix material, are proposed. Natural fibers such as hemp [1], bamboo [2] and kenaf [3] are light, strong, renewable, environmental friendly and cheap. Many attempts that use the natural fibers practically have been performed. For example, hemp fiber/epoxy, flax fiber/polypropylene (PP), and kenaf/PP are particularly attractive in automotive applications due to lower cost and lower density. For general, glass fibers used for composites have density near of 2.6 g/cm³ and cost about \$1.5/kg. However, flax fibers have a density of 1.55g/cm³ and cost between \$0.2 and \$1.2/kg [4]. Natural fiber composites are, also, claimed to offer environmental advantages such as reduced dependence on non-renewable energy/material sources, lower pollutant emissions, lower greenhouse gas emissions, enhanced energy recovery, and end of life biodegradability of components. Since, such superior environmental performance is an important driver of increased future use of natural fiber composites, a thorough comprehensive analysis of the relative environmental impacts of natural fiber composites and conventional composites, covering the entire life cycle, is warranted [5]. Many researchers concerned about natural fiber compound with thermal and biodegradable polymer [6-7]. They used short natural fibers as reinforcement. Few articles concerning about using a fabric type of

natural fiber as a reinforced material. Therefore, we attempted to use a three-dimensional structure of jute as reinforcement. To create a 3D natural fiber composite that has good mechanical properties like as the common used glass fiber reinforced plastics. The manufacturing techniques of 2D plain jute fabric and 3D orthogonal jute fabric reinforced epoxy and PLA composites are discussed in this paper. The tensile, compressive, bending, and impacting properties were, also, performed in the current study.

1. Experimental

1.1 Materials

Commercial products of 2-D plain jute fabrics (13 picks/inch, 15 ends/inch and five count/yarn) were used to reinforce epoxy and PLA resin to get a referred material. A jute yarns with count of 3 were used to weave 3-D fabrics. The epoxy resin system (AW 56A and AW56C, Yi-Bo Chemical Co. Ltd., Taiwan) and PLA chips (NCP0004, Wei Mon Industry Co. Ltd., Taiwan), were used as matrix materials. The epoxy resin which has low viscosity and can be cured under room temperature is beneficial for the manufacturing of 3D jute/epoxy composites. Sodium hydroxide was used to purify the jute fibers.

1.2 Treatment of jute fibers

Prior to weaving process, the jute fibers were treated with starch to improve the fiber strength which should be resisting the weaving force. After the weaving process, jute fabrics were treated with an alkali solution in a canister. The fabric to 2 wt. % Na_2SO_3 and 5 wt. % NaOH solution ratios was 1:2:10 by weight. The treating temperature was 120°C for 60 min. The 3D fabrics were then washed in a tank for 60 min to remove chemical residues until a fabric pH of about 7 was obtained.

1.3 Fabric weaving

Two types (2D plain and 3D orthogonal) of jute fabrics were used in the current experiment. Schematics of the fabrics are shown in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the 3D preform has three sets of yarn which vertical to each other, it called orthogonal. Due to the orthogonal structure of the preform, a Dobby loom had been modified to weave the preform [8]. The weave pattern of the 3D orthogonal fabric is shown in Fig. 2. Each yarn in x-, y-, and z-direction should be tension controlled well by a yarn supplied system which differs from a conventional warp beam. The good weaving of 2D plain jute fabrics and 3-D orthogonal jute fabrics are shown in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. The fabric densities of 3D fabric are 22 ends per inch in x-direction, seven

ends per inch in y-direction and 14 ends per inch in z-direction. The thickness of 3D fabric is 3.2 mm.

1.4 Composites manufacturing and testing

Four composites, 2D plain jute fabric reinforced epoxy (2D/epoxy), 3D orthogonal jute fabric reinforced epoxy (3D/epoxy), 2D plain jute fabric reinforced PLA (2D/PLA), and 3D orthogonal jute fabric reinforced PLA (3D/PLA) were made in the experiment. The manufacturing process of 2D and 3D jute fabrics reinforced epoxy composites is illustrated in Fig. 4. All the jute fabrics should be dried in an oven for 24 h at 90°C prior to the resin impregnation. For the manufacturing of 2D/epoxy composites, five 2D plain jute fabrics were impregnated the epoxy resin by hand lay-up method. The impregnated 2D fabrics were vacuumed for two hours to release void and cured at hot-press machine under 60°C for two hours and 90°C for two hours. The post cure temperature is 120°C for two hours under a press of 50 psi at the hot-press machine (Fig. 5). For the manufacturing of 3D/epoxy composites, a resin dipping tank, which is a box made by release paper, was used to impregnate with the resin. The 3D jute fabrics were dipped into the epoxy compounds solution in the tank for one hour and then vacuumed for two hours. The curing process was carried out in according to fig. 5. Firstly, we set the tank in an oven with vacuum under 60°C for two hours. Secondly, we changed the impregnated 3D fabrics in a mold, covered with a steel panel to flat the composite under 90°C for two hours. Finally, the impregnated 3D fabrics were cured under 120°C for two hours to finish the 3D/epoxy composites manufacturing.

However, the mentioned technique for epoxy based composites cannot be used to make thermoplastic composites. The process of making jute/PLA composites is shown in Fig. 6. Resin film molding method has been performed to make the 2D/PLA and 3D/PLA composites. In the PLA film preparation, thirty grams of PLA chips were molded to film with one mm in thick on a hot press machine under 190°C for three minutes. Not only the jute fabrics (2D and 3D) but also the PLA films should be preheated in an oven at 60°C for 24 hours prior to the stacking process. Fig. 7 shows the stacking sequence for the making of 2D/PLA composites. Eight PLA films and five 2D plain jute fabrics were stacked and heated under 190°C for 3 minute on the hot press. Each layer of fabric covered with one layer of PLA film excluded the middle layer of plain jute fabric. There were two PLA films covered with up and down the middle layer. For 3D/PLA composite, the 3D orthogonal jute fabric was stacked between 12 layers of PLA films (Fig. 8). The stacked materials

were set in a mold and heat by a compression molding press at 190°C for three minimums at 700 PSI pressure. Cooling was done under the same pressure by placing the molding between the two cold plates on which set the pressure. All the composites are A4 size. The composite thickness was controlled at 3.5 mm by a mold. As shown in table 1, the weight contents are about 32% and 30% for 2D and 3D composites, respectively. The void content was 3% for the 2D composite and 4.2% for the 3D composite. The 2D/epoxy, 3D/epoxy, 2D/PLA, and 3D/PLA composites are, also, shown in figure 9(a) , 9(b), 9(c), and 9(d).

Tensile tests were performed using a MTS 810 system, in accordance with ASTM D3039 standards. The specimens were tested at a rate of 2 mm per minute. The elastic modulus and tensile strength were calculated from the stress-strain curve. Compressive and three-point bending tests were performed on the same machine as per ASTM D3410 and ASTM D790-03 standards, respectively. Impact tests were performed on an Izod impact testing machine. The test method adopted was consistent to ASTM D256 method A. All the test specimens were notched with a radius of 0.25mm. All the mechanical properties reported to represent the average value of five readings at least.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 Tension and Compression

Fig. 10 shows the tensile strength of jute/epoxy composites. The tensile strengths of 2D/epoxy or 3D epoxy composites are about 10% to 25% higher than that of pure epoxy. For tensile modulus in jute/epoxy composites, the 2D/epoxy is 187% and 101% higher than that of pure epoxy and 3D/epoxy composites, respectively. The tensile strength and modulus of jute/PLA composites are shown in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13. The peak stress of 2D/PLA composite is higher than that of 3D/PLA composite. Moreover, the failure strain of 3D/PLA composite is larger than that of 2D/PLA composite. The difference was caused by the fiber architecture of jute fabrics. The 3D orthogonal fabric is less dense. It is easy to elongate the fiber under tension. So, the tensile modulus of 3D/PLA composite is lower than that of 2D/PLA composite. Both the 2D plain and the 3D orthogonal jute fabrics possess the reinforced effect in tensile strength to the pure epoxy and PLA resin. However, the 3D orthogonal fabric has less reinforced efficiency than 2D plain fabrics. This phenomenon could be induced by the 3D orthogonal constructions. The 3D orthogonal fabric possesses

much resin rich region caused to larger deformation while testing.

The compressive results are shown from fig. 14 to fig. 17. Both the 2D and 3D jute fabrics reinforced epoxy and PLA composites have a similar scale on compressive strength. The value was about 10% and 20% higher than pure epoxy and pure PLA sample, respectively. It indicated that the resin domain the longitudinal compressive strength of 2D and 3D jute reinforced epoxy and PLA composites. For compressive modulus, the 2D/epoxy composite was 39% and 19.5 % higher than that of pure epoxy and 3D/epoxy samples. The 3D/epoxy composites have less reinforced efficiency than 2D/epoxy in compression. Furthermore, in jute fabric reinforced PLA composites, the 2D/PLA composite has good reinforced effect in compression. The compressive modulus of 2D/PLA composite is 50% than that of pure PLA sample; in the meanwhile, the 3D/PLA composite is 21.5% high.

Over all, the reinforced effect of 2D jute fabric is higher than that of 3D jute fabric while tension and compression.

2.2 Bending and Impact

The three-point bending results are reported in fig. 18 and fig. 19. Both the 2D fabrics and 3D fabrics have reinforcing effect on the bending strength and modulus. The 2D/epoxy composites have 52.3% higher than that of pure epoxy sample, and the 3D/epoxy composites have 110% stronger than that of pure epoxy sample. It, also, can be found in fig. 18 and fig. 19 that the 3D/epoxy composites have better bending strength and modulus than that of 2D/epoxy composite. Even in jute/PLA composites, the 3D/PLA composites possess good bending resistance. The z-yarn can inhibit the crack propagating through the in-plane direction, that is, to inhibit the delamination occurred. The strain energy of the jute fabrics reinforced epoxy and PLA composites under tension, compression, and bending are summarized in table 1. The strain energy is calculated automatically by the MTS 810 system based on the load-displacement relations. It indicated the materials inhibit internal work to resist external force. Summarizing table 1, we found that the epoxy based composites have better strain energy than the PLA based composites.

The results of Izod impact for the epoxy based and PLA based jute fabric composites are shown in fig. 20. Both the 2D and 3D jute fabrics improved the impact energy absorption. For PLA based composites, the impact energy for 2D/PLA or 3D/PLA composites is 15% in average higher than

that of pure PLA sample. It also has 35% improved for epoxy based composites. The same as the bending results, the 3D fabric has good ability to resist the impact loading.

2.3 Failure

The tensile failure images are shown in Fig. 21. The 2D composite broke across the width. The 3D composite damage occurred around the resin rich region and pass through the width of the specimen. For compression, the 2D composite bent at the central of the specimen and the grid position (Fig. 22(a)). It was quite different than that of the 3D composite in compression. The kinked phenomenon could be found in 3D composites while longitudinal compression. The 3D specimen kinked on the area of fixed tabs (Fig. 22(b)). Observation of the three-point bending history, it can find the both the composites failed starting from the tensile side to the compressive side. However, the z-yarn in the 3D composite can stop the damage propagated along the in-plane direction (Fig.23). Finally, the IZod impact failure photographs could be found in Fig.24. The 2D composite broke into two pieces and the weft jute yarns were been split (Fig.24 (a)). The 3D composite damaged with z-yarn and y-yarn breaking (Fig. 24 (b)).

Conclusions

The jute fiber can be used to weave a three-dimensional preform by pre-treating the fiber with a starch solution and controlling the tension while weaving. The 2D plain jute fabric composites are good in tension. And the 3D orthogonal jute fabric composites are good in flexural strength and impact energy absorption. For compression, the 2D and 3D composites have the equivalent characteristics. In addition, both the jute fabrics possess the reinforced effect to enhance the mechanical properties of epoxy and PLA resin. Natural fiber seems to be the potential in the application of loading structure by treatment the fiber to have a strong structure, such as three-dimensional weaving or braiding. Therefore, applying the weaving technique to enhance the natural fiber seems to be a good research topic. By the way, strong weaving structures caused a challenge to impregnate with matrix, especially in thermoplastic resin. So, that how to increase the fiber content of jute fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite is another study topic.

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(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Schematics of 2D plain fabric (a) and 3D orthogonal fabric (b).

Fig. 3. Photos of 2D plain jute fabric (a) and 3D orthogonal jute fabric.

Fig. 2. Weave pattern of 3D orthogonal fabric.

Fig. 4. Manufacturing process of jute fabrics (2D and 3D) reinforced epoxy composites.

Fig. 5. Curing cycle for epoxy resin.

Fig. 6. Manufacturing process of jute fabrics (2D and 3D) reinforced PLA composites.

Fig. 7. Stacking sequence for the manufacturing of 2D plain jute fabric reinforced PLA composites.

Fig. 8. Stacking sequence for the manufacturing of 3D orthogonal jute fabric reinforced PLA composites.

Fig. 9. Photos of 2D/epoxy (a), 3D/epoxy (b), 2D/PLA (c), and 3D/PLA (d) composites.

Table 1. The fabric structure, fiber weight content and matrix constituent of specimen nomination

	Fiber	Fabric Structure	Matrix	Wf(%)
2D/PLA	Jute	2D Plain	PLA	32
3D/PLA	Jute	3D Orthogonal	PLA	30
2D/Epoxy	Jute	2D	Epoxy	32
3D/Epoxy	Jute	3D Orthogonal	Epoxy	30

Fig. 10. Tensile strength of jute/epoxy composites.

Fig. 11. Tensile modulus of jute/epoxy Composites.

Fig. 14. Compressive strength of jute/epoxy composites.

Fig. 12. Tensile Strength of Jute/PLA Composites.

Fig. 15. Compressive modulus of jute/epoxy composites.

Fig. 13. Tensile Modulus of Jute/PLA Composites.

Fig. 16. Compressive strength of jute/PLA composites.

Fig. 17. Compressive modulus of jute/PLA composites.

Fig. 20. Impact energy of jute/epoxy and jute/PLA composites.

Fig. 18. Bending strength of jute/epoxy and jute/PLA composites.

Table 2 Strain energy of jute composites under tension, compression, and bending. (Unit: N*mm)

Force Sample	Tension	Compression	Bending
Pure Epoxy	2610.4	2726.9	883.9
2D/Epoxy	3280.6	3221.4	724.8
3D/Epoxy	2876.5	3329.7	943.3
Pure PLA	1136.8	1961.3	642.1
2D/PLA	1426.8	1985.7	378.8
3D/PLA	1206.6	2985.8	502.9

Fig. 19. Bending Modulus of jute/epoxy and jute/PLA composites.

Fig. 21. Failure photos of the composites after tension.

(a) 2D (b) 3D
 Fig. 22. Compressive failure images.

(a) 2D

(b)3D

Fig. 23. Failure images of the composites after bending.

(a) 2D

(b) 3D

Fig. 25. Failure images of the composites after impacting.